

Socioeconomic impact

Impact of modern mangrove swamp rice varieties in Sierra Leone and Guinea

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Guinea and Sierra Leone account for 46% of the total cultivated area of mangrove swamp rice in West Africa. WARDA and Sierra Leone Rice Research Station started a major rice improvement program in 1976 that targets about 200,000 ha of mangrove swamps cultivated to rice in the region. Several modern varieties (MVs), including ROK5, ROK10, Kuantik Kundur, and CP4, have been developed for and diffused across mangrove swamp rice ecologies.

We studied diffusion and adoption patterns and economic benefits of these varieties for smallholder farmers in the principal mangrove swamp rice areas in Guinea (Coyah Region) and Sierra Leone (Great Scarcies Region).

Farmers ranked the 10 most important mangrove swamp rice varieties that they grow. Based on frequency of farmers in Sierra Leone growing the varieties, ROK5 was ranked 3d, ROK10 5th, and Kuantik Kundur 7th. In Guinea, ROK5 was the only MV of any importance. Farmers ranked it as the 5th most important variety grown.

In Sierra Leone, percentage of farmers adopting at least one of these MVs increased from 5% in 1986 to 52% in 1990. In Guinea, adoption of MVs was a more recent phenomenon: in 1989, only 1% had adopted a MV; in 1990, 17% had (see figure). In Sierra Leone, 11% of total mangrove rice area was planted to MVs in 1988 and 21% in 1990. In Guinea, rice area under MVs increased from 2% in 1989 to 9% in 1990. Mean share of total rice area under MVs in the two countries rose from 9% in 1988 to 16% in 1990.

Farmers' perceptions of specific varietal characteristics of MVs, including ease of cooking, ease of threshing, tillering capacity, and yield, determine adoption behavior. Results run contrary to widely accepted views in the adoption-diffusion

Adoption and impact of improved rice varieties: regional impacts in the Coyah Region of Guinea and the Great Scarcies Region of Sierra Leone, 1986-90.

Item	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990
<i>Share of total mangrove rice area in improved varieties (rate of adoption) (%)</i>					
Guinea	-	-	-	2	9
Sierra Leone	4	5	11	18	21
<i>Farm-level impact (US\$ million)</i>					
Guinea	-	-	-	0.06	0.3
Sierra Leone	0.92	1.2	2.5	4.2	4.9
<i>Share of income from mangrove rice coming from improved varieties (%)</i>					
Guinea	0	0	0	3	13
Sierra Leone	6	7	16	25	28
<i>Cumulative impact (1986-90) (US\$ million)</i>					
Guinea	0.36				
Sierra Leone	13.7				
Total	14.1				

literature that it is farmer and farm-specific or institutional factors that condition adoption behavior of farmers.

Economic impact of MVs was studied at farm level in villages and at the regional level. Farm-level economic benefits were computed using data on incremental changes in area under MVs, average yield differences between MVs and local varieties, farm households' cultivated rice area under MVs, and rice price. Use of cash inputs to produce MVs, such as fertilizers and herbicides, was extremely

rare, so farmers had no additional variable costs when adopting MVs.

Cumulative farm-level economic impact of MVs (see table) was estimated to be US\$14 million in the Great Scarcies Region from 1986 to 1990, and \$0.4 million in Coyah Region (which mainly captures economic benefits since 1990). Future economic impact of MVs in Guinea should increase substantially given the dramatic increase in farmers growing MVs in both countries during the past several years and the possibility of even greater adoption. ■